

Exploring the role of Digital Affordances in Fostering Critical Democratic Citizenship among Residents of Edo State, Nigeria

Hassan Otinau, PhD

Department of Mass Communication
University of Benin, Benin, Edo State
otinauhassan@gmail.com; 08063398592

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20313913>

Abstract

This study explored the role of digital affordances in fostering critical democratic citizenship among residents of Edo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the research seeks to: (1) assess the extent to which residents use social media platforms (Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter) to engage with governance issues, and (2) examine the contributory effect of these platforms on critical democratic citizenship engagement. The study is anchored on affordance theory which explains the technological possibilities and limitations of social media; critical citizenship theory provides insight into the characteristics of active, justice-oriented democratic participation; and Habermas's public sphere theory examines the potential for genuine public discourse in digital spaces. This combined framework guides the exploration of how social media affordances shape citizens' engagement in critical democratic practices in Edo State, Nigeria. Utilising a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from 400 respondents across urban, semi-urban, and rural areas of Edo State. The findings reveal a strong positive correlation ($R = 0.840$) between social media use and critical democratic citizenship, with WhatsApp ($B = 19.106$, $p = 0.000$) and Twitter ($B = 16.175$, $p = 0.000$) emerging as the most significant platforms for fostering civic engagement. Facebook, however, showed limited impact ($B = 1.585$, $p = 0.294$), likely due to its diverse usage patterns. The findings highlighted the importance of digital platforms in enabling citizens to engage in political discourse, critique governance and mobilise for social change. The study concluded that while social media has the potential to enhance democratic participation, its effectiveness depends on digital literacy, platform design, and the socio-political context. The study recommended that government and non-governmental organisations should invest in digital literacy programs to equip citizens with the skills needed to critically evaluate online information, engage in constructive political discourse, and navigate social media platforms effectively while efforts should be made to bridge the digital divide, particularly in rural areas, by improving internet infrastructure and providing affordable access to digital devices.

Keywords: Digital Affordances, Fostering, Critical, Democratic Citizenship and Residents of Edo State

Introduction

Social media platforms have become integral to daily life, with over 5.24 billion users worldwide as of January 2025, representing 63.9% of the global population. On average,

users spend approximately 143 minutes per day on these platforms, demonstrating their widespread reach and influence (Datareportal, 2025; Statista, 2025). In the political sphere, social media has transformed citizen engagement and information dissemination. Platforms like Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok have become essential tools for political discourse, campaigning, and civic participation, allowing individuals to bypass traditional media gatekeepers and directly access political content (Disa, 2024). Governments worldwide have expressed frustration over their diminished control in this evolving media landscape.

In exploring the relationship between affordances and critical democratic citizenship among residents of Edo State, Nigeria, it is essential to understand these key terms. The concept of affordance refers to the potential actions or possibilities for interaction that an environment or object offers to an individual, based on the interaction between their abilities and the environment's properties (Gibson, 1979). Critical democratic citizenship extends beyond the legal status of being a citizen; it emphasises active, reflective participation in democratic processes, critical thinking, and advocacy for social justice. This concept captures the idea that true democratic engagement requires individuals to question norms, voice dissent, and participate meaningfully in governance (Council of Europe, 2012). In the broader context of governance, defined by the World Bank (1992) as responsive, inclusive and law-driven, Nigeria presents a complex case. Governance in Nigeria encompasses a mix of formal and informal institutions, influenced by businesses, non-governmental organizations, and citizens, shaping decision-making and resource distribution (Kooiman, 2003).

Edo State has been at the forefront of digital transformation in Nigeria. The state launched the Edo State Open Data Portal in 2013, the first sub-national portal in Africa, aiming to establish a broader framework for an Open Government ecosystem (World Bank, 2014). In 2024, Edo State unveiled a commemorative plaque to celebrate its transition from paper-based to digital governance, positioning itself as the first in Nigeria to adopt full-scale e-governance (Edo State Government, 2024). The 2020 gubernatorial election in Edo State serves as a pivotal case study to examine the relationship between social media and voter behavior. The election witnessed intense political campaigns on social media, with movements like "Edo No Bi Lagos" advocating against political godfatherism and promoting free electoral choice (Adebayo, 2021). This heightened political participation through social media has the potential to foster more inclusive democratic processes, amplify marginalised voices, and influence political outcomes. However, challenges such as the spread of misinformation, the digital divide, and online harassment pose significant concerns (Adegoke & Oso, 2015; Andover *et al* 2024).

By analysing the affordances of digital platforms and their role in promoting critical democratic citizenship among Edo State residents, this research aims to understand how digital engagement shapes civic participation in Nigeria's evolving governance landscape.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the transition to the Fourth Republic in 1999, governance in Nigeria continues to face significant challenges marked by corruption, poor public service delivery, and limited accountability. World Bank (2023) estimates that 40% of Nigerians live below

the poverty line, highlighting the persistence of widespread socio-economic inequality. Additionally, Transparency International's Corruption Perceptions Index consistently ranks Nigeria among the most corrupt countries globally, standing at 140 out of 180 nations in 2024 (Transparency International, 2024). These indicators suggest that democratic governance has not translated into substantial improvements in citizens' quality of life.

Popular revolts and civic activism, such as the #EndSARS movement of 2020, have demonstrated the growing dissatisfaction among citizens regarding police brutality, poor governance, and the lack of accountability. Despite the mass mobilisation of youths and widespread calls for reform, the political class has largely remained unresponsive, with limited systemic changes resulting from these movements (Okunola, 2021). The Twitter ban of 2021, following President Muhammad Buhari's controversial tweet, further exemplifies the strained relationship between the government and citizens, especially regarding digital expression and accountability (Ojebode & Adegbola, 2022).

Social media have emerged as a critical platform for political discourse and activism, offering citizens a channel to challenge state power, expose corrupt practices, and demand accountability. Platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram have become digital arenas for citizens to critique governance and mobilise for change. However, the extent to which these affordances foster critical democratic citizenship—characterised by active and reflective participation, remains underexplored, particularly in specific states like Edo State. Edo State presents a unique case for examining this dynamic, given its history of political engagement and digital transformation initiatives; yet, there is limited scholarly attention to how residents of Edo State use social media to hold government agencies accountable and whether these digital engagements effectively influence governance. Understanding the relationship between digital affordances and citizens' efforts to promote accountability in Edo State is crucial for evaluating the role of social media in enhancing democratic governance within the Nigerian context. It is against this backdrop that this study explored the role of digital affordances in fostering critical democratic citizenship amongst residents of Edo State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Assess the extent to which residents of Edo State use social media platforms (Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Twitter) to engage with governance issues.
2. Examine the contributory effect of social media platforms on critical democratic citizenship engagement among Edo State residents.

Political Engagement and Participation

Political engagement is central to critical democratic citizenship. Traditionally, engagement occurs through formal processes like voting or joining political parties. However, social media has introduced informal spaces for political expression, such as online activism and petitions. Platforms like Twitter and Facebook enable citizens, particularly youth, to participate in civic discussions, mobilise for change, and hold

authorities accountable. For instance, during Nigeria's #EndSARS protests in 2020, social media played a pivotal role in organising demonstrations and advocating for police reform. Despite this potential, there is limited understanding of how digital engagement translates into tangible democratic outcomes, especially in regions like Edo State.

Challenge to Authority and Power Structures

A key aspect of democratic citizenship is the willingness to challenge authority and hold power accountable. Social media provides tools for citizens to critique leaders, expose corruption, and demand transparency. In Nigeria, these affordances often conflict with political elites' attempts to control information, as seen in internet shutdowns or social media restrictions. The struggle to balance state power and citizens' right to free expression remains a critical concern for democratic citizenship.

Critical democratic citizenship goes beyond legal citizenship, emphasising active participation, critical reflection, advocacy for justice and the courage to challenge power structures (Westheimer & Kahne, 2004). This literature review explores how social media affordances contribute to these dimensions, drawing on empirical studies to examine their impact on political engagement, critical reflection, advocacy for social justice, deliberative dialogue, and collective action.

Social media and Critical Democratic engagement

Social media have become a crucial space for informal political engagement, allowing citizens to bypass traditional channels and directly voice their opinions (Bennett *et al* 2011). Skoric *et al* (2016) found that interactive features like commenting and sharing reduce barriers to political participation, enabling individuals to mobilise for political causes and engage in public debates. This was evident during Nigeria's #EndSARS protests in 2020, where social media facilitated rapid information sharing, mobilisation, and advocacy against police brutality (Okunola, 2021). These findings highlight the role of social media in fostering political engagement, particularly among youth and marginalised groups. Critical reflection involves assessing social and political systems, questioning unjust policies and developing awareness of systemic inequalities. Aalbers *et al* (2019) found that individuals with higher levels of critical media literacy are more likely to question the credibility of online sources, seek diverse perspectives, and critically assess information. While social media provides opportunities for critical reflection, it also poses challenges due to misinformation and echo chambers, which can limit exposure to diverse viewpoints and hinder the development of a well-informed citizenry.

Deliberative dialogue, which involves open, rational, and respectful discussions aimed at understanding diverse perspectives, is essential for democratic citizenship. Habermas's (1989) theory of the public sphere underscores the importance of such dialogue in democratic societies. Halpern & Gibbs (2013) found that while social media can facilitate deliberation, the quality of discussions varies widely. Factors like platform design and community norms play a significant role in determining whether dialogue is

constructive or polarising, highlighting the need for platforms that encourage inclusive and respectful discourse.

Social media affordances, such as rapid information dissemination and decentralised communication, lower the barriers to organising collective action (Tufekci, 2017). Tufekci's research demonstrated how social media enabled activists to coordinate large-scale protests swiftly, as seen in the Arab Spring and global movements like #EndSARS.

Theoretical Framework

The study is grounded in affordance theory, critical citizenship theory and Habermas's public sphere theory. These frameworks collectively provide a lens for understanding how social media platforms influence citizens' ability to engage in democratic processes, advocate for justice, and challenge power structures.

Affordance Theory (Gibson, 1979; Norman, 1988)

Affordance theory, developed by James J. Gibson (1979), describes the action possibilities that an environment or object offers to an individual based on their abilities. Donald Norman (1988) extended this concept to digital interfaces, highlighting how user interactions with technology are shaped by perceived affordances. In the context of social media, affordances refer to features like liking, commenting, and sharing that enable or constrain users' engagement in political discourse and civic participation. Applying affordance theory to this study allows an exploration of how social media platforms serve as tools for political engagement, critical reflection, advocacy, and collective action. While social media affordances can reduce barriers to participation and amplify marginalised voices, they can also lead to misinformation, echo chambers, and online harassment, potentially undermining democratic engagement.

Critical Citizenship Theory (Westheimer & Kahne, 2004):

Critical citizenship theory emphasizes active, reflective, and justice-oriented participation in democratic processes. Westheimer and Kahne (2004) categorise citizenship into three types: personally responsible, participatory, and justice-oriented. This study focuses on the justice-oriented aspect, where citizens actively question power structures, challenge injustice, and advocate for systemic change. In Edo State, where governance challenges like corruption and inequality persist, social media becomes a platform for critical citizenship. Social media affordances enable citizens to question authority, critique policies, and mobilise for social justice. However, the effectiveness of these actions in translating into meaningful democratic change remains underexplored.

Habermas's Public Sphere Theory (1989):

Habermas's theory of the public sphere conceptualises a space where citizens engage in open, rational, and critical debate about societal issues. According to Habermas (1989), a functioning public sphere is essential for a healthy democracy, as it facilitates inclusive

dialogue and consensus-building. Social media has been described as a “digital public sphere,” where citizens can discuss public issues, express dissent and hold power accountable. In Nigeria, where traditional media may be restricted or influenced by state actors, social media offers a relatively decentralised space for public discourse. However, challenges like misinformation, online abuse, and state censorship—evident in the 2021 Twitter ban) raise questions about the extent to which social media fosters critical, inclusive, and productive democratic dialogue.

Methodology

Nigeria had approximately 36.9 million social media users as of January 2023, representing about 17.1% of the population (Datareportal, 2023). With an estimated population of 4.8 million in Edo State (based on the National Population Commission's projections for 2023) and assuming a similar social media penetration rate, there are about 820,000 social media users in the state. Given the higher urbanisation in Edo State's capital, Benin City, the penetration rate likely ranges between 20% and 25%, potentially increasing the user base to 960,000–1.2 million. However, this estimate may vary due to disparities in internet accessibility, smartphone ownership, and urban-rural dynamics.

Using Cochran's formula for sample size determination:

$$n = (Z^2 * p * (1 - p)) / e^2$$

where:

- Z = 1.96 (95% confidence level)
- p = 0.5 (assumed maximum variability)
- e = 0.05 (margin of error)

The required sample size was calculated as approximately 385, which was rounded up to 400 for convenience. This sample size is sufficient to ensure generalisability and robust statistical analysis (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2019). A stratified sampling technique was applied to distribute the sample of 400 respondents across urban, semi-urban, and rural areas of Edo State. This approach considered the varying levels of social media penetration and population density:

- Urban Areas (Benin City: Oredo, Egor, Ikpoba-Okha): 50% (200 respondents).
- Semi-Urban Areas (Auchi, Ekpoma, Uromi, Irrua): 30% (120 respondents).
- Rural Areas (Other 14 LGAs): 20% (80 respondents).

Benin City, as the most urbanised and digitally connected area, received a higher proportion of the sample, while rural areas with lower internet access had a smaller representation.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on an adapted version of the Critical Democratic Citizenship (CDC) scale by Gil de Zúñiga, Jung & Valenzuela (2012). The questionnaire captured demographic variables (age, gender, education, occupation, and religion) and measured engagement with social media on political and governance issues. The CDC scale consisted of 20 items divided into five thematic subscales:

- Good Governance Issues Discussed on Social Media (4 items)
- Engagement with Government Policies (4 items)
- Criticism of the Democratic Process (4 items)
- Encouragement of Participation in Democratic Processes (4 items)
- Relationship Between Government Performance and Critical Democratic Citizenship (4 items)

Responses were recorded using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (5).

Data were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 26. Composite scores for each respondent were computed by summing the scores of all 20 items, yielding a range of 20 to 100. Higher scores indicate greater engagement with critical democratic citizenship. The following analyses were conducted:

- Descriptive Statistics: Means, medians, and standard deviations were used to summarize the data.
- Regression Analysis: The CDC scale was the dependent variable, while Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Twitter usage were the independent variables.
- Reliability Testing: Cronbach’s alpha was used to evaluate the internal consistency of the CDC scale.

Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained digitally before completing the survey.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	273	68.8%
	Male	124	31.2%
Age	18–20 years	3	0.8%
	26–30 years	145	36.5%
	36–40 years	57	14.4%
	46–50 years	58	14.6%
Education	Undergraduate	18	4.5%
	First Degree/Diploma	181	45.6%
	Postgraduate Degree	198	49.9%
Religion	Christian	319	80.4%
	Muslim	73	18.4%
	African Traditional/Other	5	1.3%
Employment Status	Public/Private Sector	247	62.2%

Self-Employed	110	27.7%
Student	24	6.0%
Unemployed	16	4.0%

The table 1 above reveals gender disparity among the respondents, with females (273) making up a significant majority at 68.8%, while males (124) constitute only 31.2%. This uneven distribution suggests that the data predominantly reflects a female perspective. The largest group of respondent falls within the 26–30 age bracket (145, 36.5%), followed by those aged 46–50 (58, 14.6%) and 36–40 (57, 14.4%). The younger age group of 18–20 years is notably underrepresented, with only (3, 0.8%) respondents, suggesting that the sample is skewed towards more mature individuals who may have more established viewpoints on governance and political issues. The majority of respondents hold a postgraduate degree (198, 49.9%), while a significant portion has a first degree or diploma (181, 45.6%). Only a small fraction (18, 4.5%) are undergraduates, indicating that the survey primarily represents a highly educated population whose responses may be shaped by their advanced academic exposure. A predominant majority of respondents identify as Christian (319, 80.4%), while Muslims account for a smaller segment (73, 18.4%). A minor proportion (5, 1.3%) adheres to African Traditional Religion or other beliefs, reflecting a religious composition that is not entirely diverse. The majority of respondents are employed in public or private sectors (247, 62.2%), followed by self-employed individuals (110, 27.7%). Students (24, 6.0%) and unemployed persons (16, 4.0%) make up the smaller segments, suggesting that the responses primarily reflect the views of working adults with direct stakes in governance matters.

Table 2: Platform usage for Political and Governance Engagement

Platform	User Type	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Facebook	Low User	245	61.7%	61.7%	61.7%
	High User	152	38.3%	38.3%	100.0%
WhatsApp	Low User	192	48.4%	48.4%	48.4%
	High User	205	51.6%	51.6%	100.0%
Instagram	Low User	348	87.7%	87.7%	87.7%
	High User	49	12.3%	12.3%	100.0%
Twitter	Low User	243	61.2%	61.2%	61.2%
	High User	154	38.8%	38.8%	100.0%
Total		397	100.0%	100.0%	

A majority are low users, suggesting that Facebook may not be a primary platform for discussions or activities related to critical democratic citizenship. The nearly balanced distribution indicates that WhatsApp is widely used. Its strong impact in the regression analysis suggests it may be a significant space for discussions and engagement in critical democratic topics. Most participants are low users of Instagram, suggesting limited engagement with content that might influence or reflect critical democratic citizenship.

The platform's visual-centric nature may not lend itself strongly to deep political discourse. Twitter shows a higher level of high users compared to Facebook. Given its reputation as a platform for political discourse and activism this distribution.

Table 3: Regression Analysis
 Variables Entered/Removed^b

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	TWITTER_USER, INSTAGRAM, WHATSP_USER, FACEBOOK_USER ^a	.	Enter

a. All requested variables entered.

b. Dependent Variable: CDC_scale

R (Correlation Coefficient): 0.840: A strong positive correlation between social media use and scores on the Critical Democratic Citizenship (CDC) scale. This suggests that social media usage is closely related to critical democratic engagement.

R Square (Coefficient of Determination): 0.706. Approximately 70.6% of the variance in the CDC scale can be explained by the combined use of Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Twitter. This strong explanatory power suggests that social media plays a major role in shaping individuals' critical democratic consciousness. Adjusted R Square: 0.703 The slight difference from R Square suggests minimal overfitting.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.840 ^a	.706	.703	9.09876

a. Predictors: (Constant), TWITTER_USER, INSTAGRAM, WHATSP_USER, FACEBOOK_USER

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	71485.049	4	17871.262	215.869	.000 ^a
	Residual	29720.709	359	82.787		
	Total	101205.758	363			

a. Predictors: (Constant), TWITTER_USER, INSTAGRAM, WHATSP_USER, FACEBOOK_USER

b. Dependent Variable: CDC_scale

ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)

F-statistic: 215.869, p-value: 0.000 The model is highly significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming that the relationship between social media use and critical democratic citizenship is not due to chance.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardised Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.104	2.695		.410	.682
	FACEBOOK_USER	1.585	1.507	.047	1.052	.294
	WHATSP_USER	19.106	1.408	.573	13.566	.000
	INSTAGRAM	10.366	1.428	.212	7.258	.000
	TWITTER_USER	16.175	1.149	.471	14.071	.000

a. Dependent Variable: CDC_scale

Coefficients Analysis

Constant (Intercept): $B = 1.104$ ($p = 0.682$) Not significant. The baseline CDC scale score without considering social media usage is not substantial. Facebook User: $B = 1.585$, $p = 0.294$ Not significant. Facebook use does not meaningfully contribute to the CDC scale. This could imply that Facebook's broad and diverse user base dilutes its impact on critical democratic engagement.

WhatsApp User ($B = 19.106$, $p = 0.000$) is significant and the strongest predictor. WhatsApp might facilitate critical discussions and networking within closed, trust-based groups, amplifying engagement with democratic issues.

Instagram User ($B = 10.366$, $p = 0.000$) is significant, though less impactful than WhatsApp and Twitter. Given its visual nature, Instagram may contribute to critical democratic citizenship through activism campaigns or influencer-led discussions, but to a limited extent.

Twitter User ($B = 16.175$, $p = 0.000$ Strong) is significant impact. Twitter's role in real-time news dissemination, political debate, and activism aligns with its influence on critical democratic citizenship.

WhatsApp emerges as a powerful platform for critical democratic engagement, possibly due to its private, secure, and group-oriented communication dynamics. Twitter also plays a crucial role, likely due to its open and discursive nature, fostering public dialogue and exposure to diverse perspectives. Instagram has a moderate effect, potentially due to its influence on younger demographics through visual storytelling and advocacy. Facebook's limited impact might reflect its varied usage patterns — while some users engage politically, many use it for social networking, entertainment, or passive consumption.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings revealed a strong positive correlation between social media use and critical democratic citizenship among residents of Edo State, Nigeria. Specifically, WhatsApp and Twitter emerged as the most influential platforms for fostering civic engagement, critical reflection, and advocacy for social justice. WhatsApp, with its

private and group-oriented communication dynamics, facilitates trust-based discussions and networking, making it a powerful tool for political mobilisation and engagement. Twitter, known for its real-time news dissemination and open discourse, also plays a crucial role in enabling citizens to critique governance, expose corruption and demand accountability.

Instagram, while significant, had a more moderate impact on critical democratic citizenship. Its visual-centric nature may limit its effectiveness in fostering deep political discourse, though it remains a valuable platform for activism campaigns and influencer-led discussions. Facebook, on the other hand, had a limited impact, likely due to its diverse usage patterns, where many users engage in social networking and entertainment rather than political discourse.

The study also found that respondents were more reactive to governance quality than proactive in encouraging democratic participation. While they actively discussed good governance issues and perceived a strong link between government performance and civic engagement, they were less likely to motivate others to participate in democratic processes. This suggests a need for more efforts to encourage active involvement in democratic processes beyond personal critique or discussion.

Conclusion

The study concludes that social media platforms, particularly WhatsApp and Twitter, play a significant role in fostering critical democratic citizenship among residents of Edo State, Nigeria. These platforms enable citizens to engage in political discourse, critique governance, and mobilise for social change, thereby enhancing democratic participation. However, the effectiveness of social media in promoting critical democratic citizenship is influenced by factors such as digital literacy, platform design and the socio-political context. While social media has the potential to democratise information access and amplify marginalised voices, challenges such as misinformation, online harassment, and the digital divide must be addressed to fully realise its potential.

Recommendations

1. The government and non-governmental organisations should invest in digital literacy programmes to equip citizens with the skills needed to critically evaluate online information, engage in constructive political discourse, and navigate social media platforms effectively.
2. Efforts should be made to bridge the digital divide, particularly in rural areas, by improving Internet infrastructure and providing affordable access to digital devices. This will ensure that all citizens, regardless of their location, can participate in digital democratic processes.
3. Social media platforms should be designed to facilitate constructive political discourse and minimise the spread of misinformation. Features such as fact-checking tools, content moderation and algorithms that promote diverse perspectives can enhance the quality of online democratic engagement.

4. The government should establish and enforce legal frameworks that protect citizens' digital rights, including freedom of expression and privacy. This will create a safer online environment for civic engagement and reduce the risk of online harassment and censorship.

References

- Aalbers, M., van der Molen, J. & Michels, M. (2019). The critical effect: Exploring the influence of critical media literacy on first-year college students' media consumption. *Journal of Communication Studies*, 67(3), 301-319.
- Adebayo, B. (2021). The impact of social media on elections in Nigeria: An assessment of 2020 gubernatorial election in Edo State. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/112737959/The_Impact_of_social_media_on_Elections_in_Nigeria_An_Assessment_of_2020_Gubernatorial_Election_in_Edo_State_Nigeria
- Adegoke, L. & Oso, L. (2015). Social media and citizens' participation in politics in a multi-cultural society like Nigeria. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/126901526/Social_Media_and_Citizens_Participations_in_Politics_in_a_Multi_Cultural_Society_like_Nigeria
- Aondover, E., Agbu, J. & Okibe, H. (2024). A review of social media as alternative medium for political participation. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ofeyi-Kayode/publication/377390598_A_Review_of_Social_Media_as_Alternative_Medium_for_Political_Participation/links/65a463dd40ce1c5902de7e26/A-Review-of-Social-Media-as-Alternative-Medium-for-Political-Participation.pdf
- Bennett, W. L., Wells, C. & Freelon, D. (2011). Communicating civic engagement: Contrasting models of citizenship in the youth web sphere. *Journal of Communication*, 61(5), 835-856.
- Carney, N. (2016). All lives matter, but so does race: Black Lives Matter and the evolving role of social media. *Humanity and Society*, 40(2), 180-199.
- Chadwick, A. (2017). *The hybrid media system: Politics and power*. Oxford: University Press.
- Council of Europe. (2012). *Compass: Manual for human rights education with young people*. London: Council of Europe Publishing.
- Durham, M. (2019). The nexus of critical citizenship and social media. *Media and Society Review*, 4(2), 150-168.
- Edo State Government. (2023). Edo State, bill and Melinda gates foundation sign landmark agreement for digital transformation of public service. Retrieved from <https://edostate.gov.ng/edo-state-bill-melinda-gates-foundation-sign-landmark-agreement-for-digital-transformation-of-public-service/>
- Edo State Government. (2024). Edo State leads nigeria's digital governance revolution (Unveils the E-Governance Plaque). Retrieved from <https://icta.edostate.gov.ng/edo-state-leads-nigerias-digital-governance-revolution-unveils-the-e-governance-plaque/>

- Fenton, N. (2016). *Digital, political, radical*. New York: Polity Press.
- Gibson, J. J. (1979). *The ecological approach to visual perception*. London: Houghton Mifflin.
- Habermas, J. (1989). *The structural transformation of the public sphere: An inquiry into a category of Bourgeois Society*. MIT Press.
- Halpern, D. & Gibbs, J. (2013). Social media as a catalyst for online deliberation? Exploring the affordances of Facebook and YouTube for political expression. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(3), 1159-1168.
- KhosraviNik, M. (2017). Social media critical discourse studies (SM-CDS). *Journal of Language and Politics*, 16(6), 823-831.
- Kooiman, J. (2003). *Governing as Governance*. London: Sage Publications.
- Norman, D. A. (1988). *The design of everyday things*. New York: Basic Books.
- Ojebode, A. & Adegbola, A. (2022). The Nigerian government's ban on Twitter: Implications for digital rights and civic engagement. *Media and Society Review*, 5(2), 102-118.
- Okunola, A. (2021). The role of social media in the #EndSARS movement. *Nigerian Journal of Digital Communication*, 4(1), 50-67.
- Skoric, M. M., Zhu, Q. & Goh, D. (2016). Platform affordances and political participation: How social media reshape political engagement. *New Media and Society*, 18(9), 1799-1817.
- Skoric, M. M., Zhu, Q. & Goh, D. (2016). Platform affordances and political participation: How social media reshape political engagement. *New Media and Society*, 18(9), 1799-1817.
- Transparency International. (2024). *Corruption Perceptions Index 2023*. Retrieved from <https://www>
- Tufekci, Z. (2017). *Twitter and Tear Gas: The Power and Fragility of Networked Protest*. Yale University Press.
- Westheimer, J. & Kahne, J. (2004). What kind of citizen? The politics of educating for democracy. *American Educational Research Journal*, 41(2), 237-269.
- World Bank. (2023). Nigeria: Population Data. *World Development Indicators*. Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org/>